

JAZZ VOCAL PERFORMANCE IN ENTERTAINMENT: PROBLEMS, SOLUTIONS, AND SEARCHES

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the problems of Estrada jazz vocal performance. Specific features of jazz vocal stylistics, shortcomings of Estrada jazz vocal school are analyzed.

Key words: Estrada-jazz, improvisation, vocal, ensemble, sound, terms, sound technique.

Musical variety is a means of actively developing emotional feelings that quickly affect a person. It is known that by getting to know music, you can enjoy music for a lifetime. In general, music is an integral part of the human psyche. Music is an art form that occupies a large place in our cultural life and plays an important role in the development of human personality.

In music, the Jazz genre teaches to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around. Music equips a person with high taste, shapes his spiritual outlook. This system has the ability to strongly influence human feelings and is an important means of introducing students to the world of sophistication and moral education.

Pop-jazz vocal works are one of the most important means of "jazz" expression. Initially, the participation of the human voice in jazz was a somewhat unusual phenomenon, because instead of free improvisation, the creator had only a sample text¹.

Pop-jazz vocals have their own characteristics - first of all, even when it comes to the simple presentation of the melody, the Jazz performer brings his own sound to it, and pop-jazz vocal improvisation (sket) differs from classical vocalization. It is based on the phraseology specific to the musical instrument.

Jazz has its own singing characteristics, which gradually changed according to the general evolution of jazz. Jazz performance is determined by the individual musical abilities of the singer. These include pop jazz vocal performance, distinctive vocal timbre and tonal characteristics.

Historically, the distinctive character of Jazz vocal performance is largely determined by its association with the blues. Therefore, it is characterized by the expansion of means of expressiveness compared to the traditional European technique, manifested in the use of glissando, falsetto, swing, nasal cavity sounds, whispering and other external sound effects.

In our country, the issue of pop jazz vocal performance remains very problematic today. If some singers master Jazz intonation and phrasing, improvise appropriately within a certain style, have excellent data, then there may be a problem with taste, creativity or English.

¹ Vintage (Eng. Vintage) Currently, the style is one of the most popular. The use of vintage style suggests scope for imagination.

It is very important for pop jazz singers to pay maximum attention to the words. Sometimes, in order to interpret American texts in English, it is necessary to communicate with speakers of this language for several years, or at least to work with each text in a way that they can freely understand and interpret it, that is, to organize its semantic content.

It is known that one of the most serious problems today is the lack of pop-jazz vocal teachers. The pop-jazz vocal school has not yet been perfectly formed. Also, great attention is paid to the technical side of work in teaching pop-jazz vocals in educational institutions. Phrases are dismantled, everything is moved up to the tone and vibrato - in general, we are talking only about technique. But developing your own style is not only a matter of technique, but also of reaching a certain personal level, of moving to a new level of the singer as an individual performer.

In the training of pop-jazz singers, great importance should be attached to the choice of repertoire, which should include works of various genres and styles. Solving the problems presented in the article is the key to training skilled singers.

Pop-jazz vocal performance means, first of all, a perfect sense of rhythm and harmony, as well as the mobility of the voice. In a jazz song, you have to feel the shape of the piece, be able to present your understanding of the melodic theme, change it. In the modern scene, pop and jazz performances are often closely related to each other, as elements of jazz music are often incorporated into pop music. A jazz vocalist should have a powerful voice with a large range, well-developed melodic and harmonic hearing.

The performance (vocal) of a pop singer is characterized by the following general characteristics:

- The singer works not only as a subject, but also as an intermediary between the object of his activity, that is, the composer and the listeners;
- implementation strives for continuous development and improvement;
- during the performance, the singer shows interest in the stage, love for the audience, and the desire to influence the audience through performing activities from the stage.
- the main goal of the performance is to achieve the maximum artistic and technical result, to show skill and high artistry;
- performance is characterized by the creation of vocal creative types of musical and artistic values, standards of interpretation of vocal works;
- performance is a unique form of creating certain interpersonal and professional relationships between singers and musicians, as well as one of the forms of audience perception;
- The special state that covers the singer during performance helps to form creative inspiration, which is a phenomenon of high tension and heightened emotions.

The art of jazz has experienced an important history of its development and today, as in the 20th century, it is being revived by the efforts of great performers.

It is worth noting that such a view of the spiritual world of each person and society, a deep and comprehensive analysis of the role and importance of such a unique source of

power in our lives, which calls a person to a conscious life and perfection, an important truth, a high meaning character means an invincible force.

The most important thing is that today, the art of music has a greater and stronger influence than other forms of art in the development of our young generation in the spirit of high spirituality. We all understand the importance of pop-jazz art, which attracts the hearts of young people.

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